

Computational study of structure and vibration of Schiff base of furfural and glycine

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Abstract : Eight conformers of Schiff base between furfural and glycine suitable for complex formation were studied using AM1, *ab initio* HF and DFT (B3LYP) methods. It was found that conformer 1 is more stable and used for further studies. DFT, HF, MP2 and AM1 calculations were carried out to study its structure. The geometry was optimized using the Eigenvector method and 6-31G* basis set was employed. Vibrational spectrum was calculated using HF, MP2 and AM1 methods. The bond lengths, bond angles, dihedrals and vibrational frequencies calculated by different methods compare each other. The Schiff base is potentially tridentate capable of binding through furan oxygen, imino nitrogen and carboxylato oxygen atoms.

Keywords : Schiff base, amino acid, computation, furfural, vibration, *ab initio*, DFT.

Introduction

There is considerable interest in the study of Schiff base compounds due to their potential applications^{1,2}. Schiff bases with an additional donor atom closer to the imino nitrogen are capable to form cavity of various sizes and this can accommodate metal ions³. There are many experimental and theoretical reports on Schiff bases⁴.

Due to the recent advancement in the quantum chemical study using semiempirical and *ab initio* an accurate description about molecular properties such as conformation⁵, structure⁶, vibration⁷ and electronic properties⁴ are possible. One of the most important developments in computational chemistry is the rise in the use of Density Function Theory (DFT)⁸.

Furfural, a well known natural compound and its derivatives are used extensively in vegetable oil, petroleum, plastic and rubber industries⁹⁻¹¹. Only few reports are available¹² for the interaction between furfural and glycine derivatives. The present paper reports the structure and vibration of furfural-glycine (fural-gly) using DFT, *ab initio* and semiempirical methods.

Results and discussion

Stability of conformers :

Although many conformers are possible for the fural-gly Schiff base, only eight conformers of *cis* and *trans* (Fig. 1) suitable for complex formation are selected. The

energies of the conformers are listed in Table 1. Conformer 1 (Fig. 1) has the lowest energy (Table 1) and it is the thermodynamically stable form. For further studies conformer 1 is used. In general the *cis* conformers are more stable than *trans* conformer.

Equilibrium geometry of stable conformer :

Calculated important structural parameters of the most stable conformer of fural-gly by different methods are presented in Table 2. The furan ring and imino nitrogen are slightly distorted from planarity due to the repulsion between furan oxygen and imino nitrogen. The carboxylic acid group is in the axial position. The carboxylato oxygen is in between imino nitrogen and furan oxygen to avoid interaction between them. Hydrogen atom in the carboxylato group can form hydrogen bond with furan oxygen and imino nitrogen. The values of bond length, bond angles and dihedral angles compare each other on the *ab initio* and DFT methods used. Thus, the geometrical parameters (Table 2) of fural-gly are reasonable. The dipole moment, Mulliken's atomic charge densities, HOMO, LUMO and band gap are given in Table 3. The dipole moment of the molecule is ~8 D and its principal axis is x. This higher dipole moment can cause its higher water solubility. Mulliken atomic charge density (Table 3) shows that fural-gly is potentially tridentate and capable of binding through furan oxygen, imino nitrogen and carboxylato oxygen atoms.

Fig. 1. Conformers of fural-gly.

Table 1. The relative stabilities of different conformers of fural-gly

Conformer	<i>Ab initio</i> /HF	DFT/B3LYP	AM1
	(kcal/mol)	(kcal/mol)	(kcal/mol)
	ΔH_f	$\Delta B3LYP$	ΔH_f
1	0.0	0.0	0.0
2	13.0938	3.5625	2.4338
3	12.6250	1.4063	1.0751
4	12.6563	2.9375	3.1818
5	19.2813	4.8750	4.1178
6	13.0938	5.3438	5.8230
7	19.3438	51.6250	45.9340
8	49.6563	36.3750	35.0538

Table 2. Important bond lengths, angles and dihedrals of fural-gly

Atom pair	HF	MP2	DFT/B3LYP
1-2	1.3387	1.3660	1.3616
2-3	1.4357	1.4214	1.4341

3-4	1.3444	1.3765	1.3712
1-5	1.3468	1.3722	1.3964
4-6	1.4691	1.4585	1.4463
6-7	1.2524	1.2894	1.2856
7-8	1.4508	1.4632	1.4768
8-9	1.5267	1.5297	1.5334
9-10	1.1811	1.2126	1.2125
9-11	1.3303	1.3583	1.3825
1-12	1.0679	1.0800	1.0773
2-13	1.0696	1.0813	1.0815
3-14	1.0705	1.0823	1.0836
6-15	1.0804	1.0939	1.0949
8-16	1.0785	1.0909	1.0844
8-17	1.0845	1.0974	1.0700
11-18	0.9491	0.9771	0.9839
1-2-3	105.7123	106.5656	106.5150
2-3-4	106.4537	107.0761	107.3240
5-1-2	110.7011	110.1115	110.6510
3-4-6	129.5025	130.2815	131.7451
4-6-7	131.7401	132.3142	132.8230
6-7-8	124.4751	121.5651	123.7271
7-8-9	111.0986	109.5439	113.8790
8-9-10	123.0426	123.5654	124.6874
8-9-11	115.8241	115.3443	117.2490
1-2-3-4	-0.6846	-0.7164	-0.6076
5-1-2-3	0.4210	0.6311	1.0578
1-5-4-6	177.8052	178.0240	179.3530
3-4-6-7	164.9831	163.2390	164.2543
4-6-7-8	-3.8126	-2.0394	1.8525
6-7-8-9	102.1238	101.0580	93.6056
7-8-9-10	111.8594	106.3060	107.5421
7-8-9-11	-68.9732	-72.9990	-75.5925

Vibrations :

The fural-gly ligands belongs to the C_1 point group and has 48 fundamental vibrations. The harmonic vibration frequencies calculated by HF and MP2 are comparable. The important vibration frequencies are given in Table 4. To account for errors due to neglecting electron and basis set incompleteness, the frequencies have been scaled by 1.12. In general, the HF vibrational frequencies are greater than MP2 vibrational frequencies. The more difference occurred in the vibrational frequency of O-H.

Table 3. Dipole moment, HOMO, LUMO, band gap and Mulliken atomic charge density of fural-gly

Dipole moment (Debye)	<i>Ab initio</i>				Mulliken atomic charge density	
	AM1	RHF	MP2		RHF	MP2
μ_x	5.001	-7.915	-8.525	1 C	-0.2856	-0.2325
μ_y	4.268	-0.092	-0.045	2 C	0.1350	0.0710
μ_z	-2.431	1.180	1.436	3 C	-0.2430	-0.2139
μ_T	7.015	8.00	8.645	4 C	0.2992	0.2690
HOMO (kcal/mol)	-	-0.3441	-0.3394	5 O	-0.6222	-0.4845
LUMO (kcal/mol)	-	0.0822	0.0661	6 C	0.0785	-0.0170
Band gap (kcal/mol)	-	0.4263	0.4055	7 N	-0.4648	-0.3352
				8 C	-0.2847	-0.3234
				9 C	0.7645	0.5885
				10 O	-0.5218	-0.4061
				11 O	-0.7166	-0.6278
				12 H	0.2360	0.2123
				13 H	0.2409	0.2133
				14 H	0.2432	0.2209
				15 H	0.2142	0.1943
				16 H	0.2348	0.2196
				17 H	0.1959	0.1855
				18 H	0.4968	0.4661

Table 4. Calculated important IR frequencies of fural-gly

HF/6-31G*	MP2/6-31G*	Assignment
3656	3337	O-H stretch
3116	3000	C-H asy. ring stretch
1849	1671	C=O stretch
1729	1514	C=N stretch
1598	1438	C=C stretch
1499	1396	C=C ring stretch
1482	1366	Acid C-O sym. stretch
1396	1302	Ring C-O sym. stretch
1368	1269	C-N stretch
1360	1242	O-H deformation
1322	1217	Ring deformation

Computation :

Semiempirical calculations were calculated using MOPAC 6¹³. All other calculations were carried out using GAMESS program¹⁴. Geometry optimizations of conformers were carried out by *ab initio* HF, MP2 and DFT/B3LYP methods. The vibrational frequencies were calculated by *ab initio* HF and MP2 methods. The 6-31G* basis set¹⁵ was used in the calculations. All the calculations were done using the Eigenvector following method. The frequencies are scaled by 1.12¹⁶.

Conclusion :

The density function, *ab initio* HF and MP2 calcula-

tions on the structure of the Schiff base of fural-gly are reported. Vibrational frequencies were calculated using HF and MP2 methods. Comparing the stability of the conformers, it is confirmed that conformer 1 is more stable. The furan ring and imino nitrogen are slightly distorted from planarity. The carboxylic acid group is in the axial position. The carboxylato oxygen is in between imino nitrogen and furan oxygen to avoid interaction between them. Hydrogen atom in the carboxylic acid group is as suitable to form hydrogen bond with furan oxygen and imino nitrogen. The ligand is potentially tridentate and capable of binding through carboxylato oxygen, imino nitrogen and furan oxygen. Vibrational frequencies are scaled.

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